

**CONCEPT OF IMPROVEMENT PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF
ESP STUDENTS BY CLIL**

(Content and Language Integrated Learning)

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(PhD)

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Annotation Teaching foreign languages, especially English for special purposes, these are certainly important, but the communicative method is a component of the grammar of the language, and their more or less use depends on the type of speech.

Key words: teach, education, concept, method, effective, language, improve, system

One of the most important tasks for the educational system of every country is to develop the most effective methods of education and to introduce them into the activities of educational institutions. If we look at it from this point of view, the attitude of our country to learning foreign languages has never been as important as it is now. Because at that time there were almost no political, economic, cultural, scientific, technical and other relations and connections with foreign countries of different systems.

Today, the implementation of political, economic, scientific-technical, cultural and educational relations with foreign countries in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan requires the introduction and improvement of advanced methods of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions due to the need to train qualified personnel who know foreign languages perfectly. For this reason, in the

years of independence, the interest and demand for improving the methods of teaching foreign languages, increasing its quality and efficiency is increasing.

It is recognized in world pedagogy that economic education is given great importance in world friendship. After all, the economy affects all spheres of society's life to a certain extent. Economic activity, as noted by Taylor, is not the priority of all sectors, but its importance is significant in any society.

The goal of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan is economic strategy and development, aimed at further improvement of tax, financial and monetary policy, as well as liberalization of foreign economic activity. It is up to the youth to fully solve these problems. Therefore, students should study the acquired economic knowledge starting from the general secondary, secondary-special vocational education systems and perfect it in the higher education system. Because the training of highly qualified economic personnel for the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most urgent problems of today.

It is known that those who enter economic higher educational institutions graduate from secondary school or secondary special vocational education institutions. Foreign language teaching should also be fully focused on the economics majors of undergraduate students. After all, whatever profession a student has chosen and what he is studying in economic higher educational institutions, he should start studying economic texts, words, expressions, and terms in foreign languages related to this profession. Because, first of all, future economists should be able to communicate freely about their chosen specialty, whether they work in joint ventures established in Uzbekistan, foreign companies or go to other foreign countries to continue their work. In today's practical language education, this language is called learning for special purposes and is opposed to the basic concept of language. So (in English, the first is called "Language for specific (special) purpose", and the second is called General or Basic sometimes Social Language).

Therefore, the basics of foreign language education are taught in the continuous education system in preschool education, primary and secondary school. After graduating from an academic lyceum and a vocational college, students who come to economic higher education institutions must learn the basics of a foreign language. Through the basics of language, the language used to communicate with people of various professions is taught through words and phrases used in everyday life, formal and informal conversations. A special language is a communication language used in business between people of the same profession. In fact, they are two different forms of the same language, mainly a division within the lexical layer of the language, the phonetic and grammatical layers of the language are common to the types of speech activity noted. It follows from this that if language education is done correctly, students should have learned foreign language phonetics, grammar and universal lexicon by the time they come to economic higher education institutions.

When teaching foreign languages, especially English for special purposes, these are certainly important, but the communicative method is a component of the grammar of the language, and their more or less use depends on the type of speech.

It is known that a child reflects in his speech what he has seen and the names of his actions from birth to school. When learning foreign languages, in particular English, it is necessary to learn the subjects, actions, customs, geographical conditions, paralinguistic features called in a foreign language only through imagination, therefore, mastering foreign languages, in particular English, is somewhat difficult. For this, we need to teach foreign languages, especially English, to speak fluently and grammatically correctly, but in the eyes of foreigners, we appear to have made a number of shortcomings. The reason is the lack of harmony between the practical life of this people and learning their language. Therefore, the introduction of video courses into the teaching process serves to create this harmony, at least a little. In today's market economy, the purchase of necessary technical

means for audio-video courses requires a lot of money. But we should not spare them money to improve the teaching of foreign languages, including English language teaching.

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